

that 10 Dq should be almost equal to the spin-pairing energy¹¹ $\pi = 2.5 B + 4 C \approx 18.5 B$ (assuming the usual relation $C \approx 4 B$). Thus taking 10 Dq = π , B (600-780 cm⁻¹) is calculated. The nephelauxetic ratio β (0.6-0.7) indicates reduction in B upon coordination, which suggests the partial covalent nature of the M-L bond¹².

The observed magnetic moments of the Co(II) adducts are in the 3.56-4.85 B.M. range. The low value of Co(OMPP)₂Py₂ (3.75 B.M.) and Co(OMPP)₂Pi₂ (3.56 B.M.) may be due to factors discussed by Stoufer *et al.*¹³. The magnetic moments of other Co(II) adducts are very close to six coordinate octahedral structure. The lower magnetic moments of the Fe(II) adducts can be attributed to the trigonal distortion of the compounds¹³. This distortion allows the excited ⁵E_g term to be mixed into the ground term by both the crystal field and spin-orbit coupling.

In view of these, the following octahedral structure for all the adducts may be suggested.

R = H or CH₃, R₁ = H or C₆H₅, R₂ = CH₃ or C₆H₅.

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Co(III) and Fe(III) Chelates of N,N'-Hexamethylene-bis-(2,5-di-OH-Acetophenone/Propionophenone/Benzophenone)†

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CHELATION properties of the Schiff bases derived from hexamethylenediamine and 2,5-di-OH-acetophenone/propionophenone/benzophenone have been studied earlier¹. The present communication deals with the synthesis and characterization of the title complexes.

Experimental

The Schiff bases, N,N'-hexamethylene-bis-(2,5-di-OH-acetophenone/propionophenone/benzophenone), were prepared by the reported method¹. Co(III) complexes were prepared by refluxing equimolar mixture of CoCl₂ and the Schiff base. Hydrogen peroxide was used for the oxidation of Co(II) to Co(III). The pH of the reaction mixture was maintained at 6.5-7 by sodium acetate buffer. Fe(III) complexes were similarly prepared from FeCl₃ and in the absence of hydrogen peroxide. The greenish-yellow and reddish-brown precipitates of Co(III) and Fe(III) complexes respectively were filtered, washed with water and ethanol and finally dried over fused CaCl₂ in a vacuum desiccator.

Physical measurements were carried out by methods reported earlier^{1,2}. Chlorine was estimated by Haywood-Kay method³.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) show 1 : 1 (metal-ligand) composition. The low molar conductance values of the complexes are ascribed to their non-electrolytic nature. The endothermic peaks observed at 122-134° in the DTA curve (Fig. 1) suggest the presence of coordinated water molecule. The TGA studies (Fig. 2) reveal that the percent weight loss upto 126-142° for the complexes corresponds to the loss of one water molecule suggesting a general formula MSB(H₂O)Cl. The complete decomposition takes place at 680-720° leaving behind metal oxides.

The band at 3240-3200 cm⁻¹ in the ligands assignable to νOH mode is retained in the complexes

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NOTES

TABLE 1—CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC DATA

Complex	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)				TGA wt. loss due to H ₂ O	Λ_M mhos cm ² mole ⁻¹	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
	Mol. Wt.	Metal	N	Cl			
CoSB ₁ (H ₂ O)Cl	470 (494.88)	12.15 (11.92)	5.79 (5.66)	7.29 (7.17)	3.62 (3.64)	4.58	0.43
CoSB ₂ (H ₂ O)Cl	500 (522.38)	11.16 (11.36)	5.26 (5.35)	6.63 (6.77)	3.32 (3.44)	3.56	0.38
CoSB ₃ (H ₂ O)Cl	640 (618.38)	9.65 (9.53)	4.62 (4.53)	5.82 (5.73)	2.78 (2.91)	2.00	0.39
FeSB ₁ (H ₂ O)Cl	410 (490.29)	11.58 (11.39)	5.84 (5.71)	7.14 (7.23)	3.82 (3.67)	3.50	6.03
FeSB ₂ (H ₂ O)Cl	526 (519.29)	10.92 (10.75)	5.50 (5.39)	6.92 (6.83)	3.59 (3.47)	2.65	5.98
FeSB ₃ (H ₂ O)Cl	645 (615.29)	9.21 (9.08)	4.70 (4.55)	5.88 (5.76)	3.04 (2.92)	2.25	5.82

TABLE 2—IR FREQUENCIES OF COMPLEXES (LIGANDS) IN cm⁻¹

Complex	ν_{OH}	ν_{OH} (Hydrogen bonded)	$\nu(C=N)$	δ_{OH} (H ₂ O)	$\rho(H_2O)$	$\nu(M-N)$	$\nu(M-O)$	$\nu(M-Cl)$
CoSB ₁ (H ₂ O)Cl	3225, 3500 (3230)	— (2780)	1630 (1645)	1610	730	450	370	320
CoSB ₂ (H ₂ O)Cl	3210, 3470 (3210)	— (2780)	1620 (1635)	1605	730	435	365	320
CoSB ₃ (H ₂ O)Cl	3240, 3485 (3240)	— (2730)	1630 (1650)	1610	725	440	365	315
FeSB ₁ (H ₂ O)Cl	3245, 3490 (3230)	— (2780)	1620 (1645)	1600	730	445	370	310
FeSB ₂ (H ₂ O)Cl	3215, 3480 (3210)	— (2750)	1620 (1635)	1600	725	450	370	315
FeSB ₃ (H ₂ O)Cl	3235, 3495 (3240)	— (2730)	1625 (1650)	1605	725	435	365	315

Fig. 1. DTA thermogram of MSB(H₂O)Cl.

Fig. 2. TGA thermogram of MSB(H₂O)Cl.

whereas the medium intensity band at 2780-2730 cm⁻¹ due to intramolecular H-bonded ν_{OH} mode^{4,5} disappears. This suggests that the ligands are partially deprotonated on complex formation. The $\nu(C=N)$ mode⁶ at 1650-1635 cm⁻¹ in the ligands shifts by 15-25 cm⁻¹ towards lower frequency region (1635-1625 cm⁻¹) in the complexes suggesting that the azomethine nitrogen is bonded to metal ion. Furthermore, the appearance of new bands at 3500-3470, 1610-1600 and 730-725 cm⁻¹ in the complexes is attributed to stretching, bending and rocking modes, respectively of coordinated water molecule⁷. The low frequency bands appearing at 450-435, 370-365 and 320-310 cm⁻¹ are tentatively assigned^{7,8} to $\nu(M-N)$, $\nu(M-O)$ and $\nu(M-Cl)$ modes, respectively. Chlorine appears to be present in the inner sphere of the complexes. The following structure can therefore be assigned to them.

R=CH₃ (H₂SB₁), R=C₂H₅ (H₂SB₂) and R=C₆H₅ (H₂SB₃);
M=Co(III) or Fe(III).

The feeble paramagnetic character of Co(III) complexes is ascribed to second order Zeeman effect with high ligand field term⁹ and we suggest the

formation of spin-paired complexes with octahedral structure. Their electronic spectra exhibit bands at 16130-15870, 19610-17860 and 26540-23260 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$ transitions, respectively¹⁰. The magnetic moment of Fe(III) complexes lies in the 5.82-6.03 B.M. range suggesting the formation of spin-free complexes with octahedral structure¹¹. These complexes absorb at 15150-14710, 17540-16150 and 22990-22220 cm^{-1} attributable to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (P), ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (F) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (F) transitions, respectively¹². Co(III) and Fe(III) diphenates also form spin-paired and spin-free complexes¹³, respectively with *o*-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl.

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Chelates of Niobium(V) and Tantalum(V) Phenoxides with 2-Hydroxyacetophenone

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NIOBIUM(V) and tantalum(V) alkoxy compounds containing β -diketones and other related ligands of composition $M(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_4 \cdot L$, $M(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_3 \cdot L_2$ and $M(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_2 \cdot L_3$ where L is benzoylacetone¹, ethyl benzoylacetate², methyl acetoacetate³ and ethyl acetoacetate have been reported. The corresponding acetylacetone complexes are also known. α -Hydroxy ketones are also known to form a large number of donor-acceptor complexes with Lewis acids^{4,5}. However, a limited number of complexes are reported in the case of 2-hydroxyacetophenone (hap). Reactions of alkoxides of aluminium⁶, titanium⁷, zirconium⁸ and germanium⁹ with α -hydroxy

carboxylic acids and salicylic acids have been carried out. Tetramethoxy and triethoxy silanes are also known to react with these acids¹⁰. In the present investigations, an attempt has been made to isolate a few chelates of niobium(V) and tantalum(V) phenoxides with 2-hydroxyacetophenone.

Experimental

Niobium(V) and tantalum(V) phenoxides of composition $M(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_5$, $M\text{Cl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_4$, $M\text{Cl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_3$, $M\text{Cl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_2$ and $M\text{Cl}_4(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)$ were prepared by published methods^{11,12}. 2-Hydroxyacetophenone (hapH) (A.R.) was used without further purification.

Compounds of composition $M(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_4 \cdot \text{hap}$ ($M = \text{Nb}$ or Ta) were prepared by refluxing either pentaphenoxides of the metals or tetraphenoxo metal(V) chlorides with the ligand. The compounds were isolated by the addition of petroleum ether or by cooling. Possible formation of the resulting compound may be visualized as follows :

Compounds of composition $M\text{Cl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_3 \cdot \text{hap}$, $M\text{Cl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_2 \cdot \text{hap}$ and $M\text{Cl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5) \cdot \text{hap}$ have been prepared by taking triphenoxy-, diphenoxy- and monophenoxy metal(V) chlorides and the ligand in benzene in 1 : 1 molar ratio and refluxing them till there was no evolution of hydrogen chloride gas. Stoichiometric composition of these compounds has been established by the estimation of metal and chlorine (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

All these compounds are fine crystalline solids and are fairly stable in dry air but change their colours on exposure to moisture. They are soluble in benzene, nitrobenzene and chloroform. Molar conductance values of millimolar solutions of the compounds in nitrobenzene (Table 1) suggest them to be non-electrolytes¹³. Molecular weight determinations of some of these compounds in nitrobenzene suggest them to be monomeric in nature.

The $\nu(\text{OH})$ stretching frequency at 3077 cm^{-1} in pure 2-hydroxyacetophenone¹⁴ (possibly due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding) is missing in all the complexes of phenoxides of niobium and tantalum which suggests that hydrogen of the hydroxyl group of the ligand is lost as hydrogen chloride gas. This is also supported by the observations that hydrogen chloride gas was evolved during the course of reaction and that phenol could be isolated from the filtrate of the complexes prepared from metal pentaphenoxides. However, no attempt was made for a quantitative estimation of phenol.